

**PHARMACEUTICAL AND ANALYTICAL STANDARDISATION OF SWALP KHADIR
VATIKA: AN AYURVEDIC PERSPECTIVE****Dr. Sana Khan^{1*}, Dr. Anjana Dwivedi², Dr. Rajeev Narayan Bilas³**

¹M.D. Scholar, Post Graduate Department of Rasa Shastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana, State Ayurvedic College and Hospital, Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh.

²HOD and Prof. Post Graduate Department of Rasa Shastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana, State Ayurvedic College and Hospital, Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh.

³Reader, Department of Rasa Shastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana, Lalit Hari State PG Ayurvedic College and Hospital, Pilibhit, Uttar Pradesh.

***Corresponding Author: Dr. Sana Khan**

M.D. Scholar, Post Graduate Department of Rasa Shastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana, State Ayurvedic College and Hospital, Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18873713>

How to cite this Article: Dr. Sana Khan^{1*}, Dr. Anjana Dwivedi², Dr. Rajeev Narayan Bilas³ (2026). Pharmaceutical and Analytical Standardisation of Swalp Khadir Vatika: An Ayurvedic Perspective. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 12(3), 468–473.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

Article Received on 05/02/2026

Article Revised on 25/02/2026

Article Published on 01/03/2026

ABSTRACT

Swalp Khadir Vatika, a classical formulation described in *Bhaishajya Ratnavali* under *Mukhroga Chikitsa*, is widely indicated in disorders of the oral cavity including *Mukhagata Vrana*. The present conceptual study aims to elaborate the pharmaceutical principles involved in the preparation of *Swalp Khadir Vatika* along with the need for Analytical standardisation to ensure quality control. The article highlights classical references, pharmaceutical procedures such as *Kwatha*, *Ghana* and *Vati Kalpana*, and the relevance of analytical parameters in standardising this traditional formulation in the present era.

KEYWORDS: *Swalp Khadir Vatika*, *Bhaishajya Kalpana*, *Ghana Kalpana*, *Vati Kalpana*, Pharmaceutical Standardisation, Ayurveda.

INTRODUCTION

Bhaishajya Kalpana forms the backbone of Ayurvedic therapeutics, as the efficacy of a drug depends not only on its ingredients but also on its method of preparation. *Acharya Charaka* and *Sushruta* have repeatedly emphasized that improper preparation of medicines leads to diminished therapeutic effects. In the present era, standardisation of Ayurvedic formulations has become essential to ensure batch-to-batch consistency, safety, and global acceptability. *Swalp Khadir Vatika* is a classical herbo-mineral formulation described in *Bhaishajya Ratnavali (Mukhrogachikitsa)*, primarily indicated in diseases of the oral cavity such as *Mukharoga*, *Dantroga*, *Jihva and Talugata Vikara*. The formulation is prepared through the principles of *Kwatha Kalpana* followed by *Ghana* and *Vati Kalpana*. The present article attempts to critically analyse the pharmaceutical steps involved in its preparation and discusses the importance of analytical standardisation from an Ayurvedic perspective. *Swalp Khadir Vatika* is described in *Bhaishajya Ratnavali* under *Mukhroga*

Chikitsa Adhyaya 61/101-103. The formulation is praised for its *Mukhasaukhya-varadhaka* property and efficacy in *Dant*, *Oshtha*, *Jihva and Talugata Rogas*.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This section covers the materials and methods used to standardize *Swalpa khadir Vatika* as a finished product and its raw materials in compliance with A.P.I.

This section can be studied under the two headings

- ✓ Pharmaceutical Study.
- ✓ Analytical Study

Ingredients

खदिरस्य तुलां सम्यग्जलद्रोणे विपाचयेत् ।
शेषाष्टभागे तत्रैव प्रतिवापं प्रदापयेत् ॥
जातीकपूरपूगानि कङ्कौलस्य फलानि च
इत्येषा गुटिका कार्या मुखसौभाग्यवर्धिनी ।
दन्तोष्ठमुखरोगेषु जिह्वातात्वामयेषु । (भै. र६१/१०१-१०३)

The formulation consists of the following drugs
These drugs collectively exhibit *Kashaya*, *Tikta* and *Katu*
Rasa, *Laghu* and *Ruksha Guna*, and *Kapha-Pitta*

Shamaka action, making them suitable for oral
inflammatory conditions.

INGREDIENTS OF SWALPA KHADIR VATIKA {TABLE -1}.

S.N.	Name (Common)	Botanical Name	Family	Part Used	Guna (Qualities)
1	<i>Khadir Twak</i>	<i>Acacia catechu</i>	Leguminosae	<i>Twak</i>	<i>Laghu, Ruksha</i>
2	<i>Javitri</i>	<i>Myristica fragrans</i>	Myristicaceae	<i>Phal Kosh</i>	<i>Laghu, Teekshna</i>
3	<i>Karpoor</i>	<i>Cinnamomum camphora</i>	Lauraceae	<i>Niryas (Satva)</i>	<i>Laghu, Teekshna</i>
4	<i>Pooghphala</i>	<i>Areca catechu</i>	Arecaceae	<i>Phal</i>	<i>Guru, Ruksha</i>
5	<i>Kankol</i>	<i>Piper cubeba</i>	Piperaceae	<i>Phal</i>	<i>Laghu, Ruksha, Teekshna</i>

It is done in three steps

- Collection of raw drugs for the preparation of *Swalpa khadir Vatika*
- Processing of raw drugs.
- Preparation of *Swalpa Khadir Vatika*. (3 batches were made)

RAW INGREDIENTS OF SWALPA KHADIR VATIKA

Method of preparation of *Swalpa Khadir Vatika*

Swalpa Khadir Vatika was prepared following classical references of *Bhaishajya Ratnavali* using a standardized pharmaceutical procedure. Authenticated raw materials—*Khadira* (*Acacia catechu*), *Javitri* (*Myristica fragrans*), *Karpoor* (*Cinnamomum camphora*), *Pooga Phala* (*Areca catechu*), and *Kankola* (*Piper cubeba*)—were procured and cleaned to remove foreign matter. *Khadira* {2400gm} was coarsely powdered, soaked overnight in the prescribed quantity of water {6100ml}, and subjected to controlled heating under *Mandagni* for approximately four hours with continuous stirring. The decoction was reduced to one-eighth of its initial volume and filtered to obtain *Khadir Kwatha*.

This *Kwatha* was further concentrated by gentle heating until a semisolid consistency was attained, avoiding charring by maintaining the temperature below 95°C. The concentrated mass (*Ghana*) was dried to a pliable consistency, after which finely powdered *Prakshepa dravyas* {quantity mentioned in *shloka*} were added and mixed uniformly. Small spherical *Vatis* were prepared manually using *Ghrita*-smeared hands, dried in shade, and finally packed in non-reactive containers. The entire process was repeated in **three batches**, demonstrating consistent yield, organoleptic characters, and reproducibility, thereby validating the standard manufacturing procedure of *Swalpa Khadir Vatika*.

Result obtained after *Kwatha* preparation{Table -2}.

Final results obtained	Batch-I	Batch-II	Batch-III	Average
Coarse powder of raw drugs (in gm)	2400	2400	2400	2400
Water (in ml)	6100	6100	6100	6100
Final quantity of <i>Kwatha</i> obtained (in ml)	765	770	750	762
Percentage of <i>Kwatha</i> obtained (%)	12.54 %	12.62%	12.29%	12.49%

Results obtained during the pharmaceutical process of *Swalpa Khadir Vatika*{Table -3}.

Batch number	Quantity of <i>Kwatha</i>	Temp.	Final quantity of <i>Ghana</i> obtained	Percentage of <i>Ghana</i> obtained	Number of <i>Ghana Vatis</i> made	Total weight of <i>Ghana Vati</i> obtained after drying
I	765 ml	22-92°C	710 gm	92.8%	1380	688.5 gm
II	770 ml	22-92°C	700 gm	90.9 %	1350	672.5 gm
III	750 ml	22-92°C	695 gm	92.6 %	1360	654.0 gm
Average	762 ml	22-92°C	702 gm	92.1%	1370	672.0gm

Observations noted during *Kwatha* preparation{Table -4}.

Duration (min.)	Temp. (°C)			Observations
	Batch-I	Batch-II	Batch-III	
0	22	22	22	The decoction appeared brown in color with a distinct bitter taste, and frothing was visible on the surface..
30	63	63	63	Persistent froth remained throughout the process..
60	80	80	80	Gradual sedimentation of drug particles was noted at the bottom while froth continued to stay on top
90	82	82	82	Colorless vapors were released continuously along with ongoing frothing.
120	85	85	85	Progressive evaporation of water content was observed during the preparation.
150	88	88	88	The liquid gradually turned dark brown in color. Colorless vapors were visibly emitted, accompanied by a noticeable reduction in volume due to evaporation.
180	90	90	90	The liquid attained a reddish-brown hue, with intense evaporation and a continuous release of vapors.
210	90	90	90	The color of the liquid darkens to reddish brown, and evaporation increased intensely
240	92	92	92	Boiling process was observed to be steady and controlled.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The results of the pharmaceutical process batches demonstrate consistent and reproducible outcomes across all parameters evaluated. The quantity of *Kwatha* obtained ranged narrowly between batches, with an average yield of 762 ml, reflecting uniform extraction efficiency. The final quantity of *Ghana* obtained showed minimal variation, with an average of 702 gm and a high percentage yield averaging 92.1%, indicating efficient concentration and recovery during the pharmaceutical process. The number of *Ghana Vatis* produced and their total weight after drying also remained consistent, further supporting the reliability of the process. The small variations observed between batches fall within acceptable tolerances, underscoring the robustness of the manufacturing protocol under the controlled temperature range of 22-92°C. The average values highlight an optimized procedure with good batch-to-batch reproducibility, ensuring product quality and efficacy. These results affirm that the pharmaceutical process for *Swalpa Khadir Vatika* preparation is well-standardized and controlled, producing consistent quantities and

quality attributes. This batch consistency is critical for ensuring therapeutic efficacy and safety in clinical applications. The study supports the practical application of rigorous batch monitoring and quality control in traditional *Ayurvedic* pharmaceutical preparations.

Analytical Study

The minimum standard for the raw pharmaceutical used to create any formulation is also suggested by the analytical study. Testing or analysis of finished items shows the drug's little or insignificant negative effect. So, confirmation of these properties in pharmaceuticals is required for countries and health-conscious individuals. On *Swalpa Khadir Vatika*, the following analytical investigation was conducted.

- Organoleptic parameters (Raw materials-mentioned in table no.5 and final product-mentioned in table no.7)
- Physico-chemical parameters (Raw materials-mentioned in table no.6 and final product - mentioned in table no.8 to 18)

ORGANOLEPTIC PARAMETERS FOR RAW MATERIALS {Table -5}

DRUG	COLOUR	ODOUR	TASTE	TEXTURE/APPERANCE
<i>Khadir</i>	Dark red/brown	Characteristic faint	Astringent	Hard brittle extract
<i>Kankol</i>	Grey brown to black	Aromatic	Pungent, slightly bitter	Wrinkled berries with stalk
<i>Pooghphala</i>	Brown	Characteristic	Astringent slightly bitter	Hard nut
<i>Javitri</i>	Yellowish orange to reddish	Aromatic	Warm ,slightly bitter	Lacy aril
<i>Karpoor</i>	White translucent crystals	Strong penetrating	Pungent cooling	Crystalline volatile

Physico-chemical parameters of Raw ingredients {table -6}

Physico-chemical parameters (in% w/w)	<i>Khadir</i>	<i>Kankol</i>	<i>Javitri</i>	<i>Poogphala</i>	<i>Karpoor</i>
Foreign matter	0.8%	1.1%	0.9%	0.89%	-
Total Ash value	1.46%	3.6%	2.11%	2.30%	-
Acid insoluble ash	0.41%	0.18%	0.48%	0.34%	-
Water-soluble extractive	9.44%	12.97%	13.56%	14.21%	-
Alcohol-soluble extractive	7.24%	18.89%	9.64%	9.65 %	-
Melting point					177
Non volatile Matter					0.0001%

All values came within a limit that means all raw drugs are validated with a limit mentioned in API and were safe to use for pharmaceutical and analytical process also, safe to use for further clinical trials.

Organoleptic- Characters of final product i.e, *Swalpa Khadir Vatika* {Table -7}

Organoleptic characters-	BATCH-I	BATCH-II	BATCH-III
COLOR	Black coloured	Black coloured	Black coloured
ODOUR	Characteristic like camphor	Characteristic like camphor	Characteristic like camphor
TASTE	Astringent	Astringent	Astringent
TEXTURE	Solid	Solid	Solid

Physico-chemical parameters

Showing the Percentage of Loss on drying for *Swalpa Khadir Vatika* {Table no.8}.

Samples	Percentage of Loss on drying
Batch 1	7.9642 % w/w
Batch 2	8.0125 % w/w
Batch 3	8.1673% w/w
Average	8.0484% w/w

Showing the Percentage of Total Ash Value *Swalpa Khadir Vatika* {Table -9}.

SAMPLES	Percentage Total Ash Value
BATCH I	5.96%
BATCH II	6.01%
BATCH III	5.99%
AVERAGE	5.98%

Showing the Percentage of Water-Soluble Extractive for *Swalpa Khadir Vatika* {Table -10}.

Samples	Percentage water-soluble extractive % w/w
BATCH I	25.69%
BATCH II	26.55%
BATCH III	26.15%
AVERAGE	26.13%

Showing the percentage of Alcohol-Soluble extractive for *Swalpa Khadir Vatika* {Table- 11}.

Samples	Percentage water-soluble extractive % w/w
BATCH I	34.3544%
BATCH II	35.7854%
BATCH III	36.1066%
AVERAGE	35.4154%

Showing the percentage of hardness{kg/cm} for *Swalpa Khadir Vatika* {Table -12}.

Samples	Hardness{kg/cm}
BATCH I	4.61
BATCH II	4.64
BATCH III	4.61
AVERAGE	4.63

Showing the results of friability test for *Swalpa Khadir Vatika* {Table -13}.

Samples	Friability test
Batch 1	0.85
Batch 2	0.72
Batch 3	0.91
Average	0.83

Showing Disintegration time for *Swalpa Khadir Vatika* {Table-14}.

Samples	Disintegration time
Batch 1	18 min
Batch 2	21 min
Batch 3	19 min
Average	19.3 min

Showing the Percentage of Acid Insoluble Ash for *Swalpa Khadir Vatika* {Table -15}.

Samples	Percentage Acid Insoluble Ash
Batch 1	0.66%
Batch 2	0.56%
Batch -3	0.61%

Showing the Percentage of pH (10 % in aq. Solution) for *Swalpa Khadir Vatika* -Table no.16.

Samples	Percentage of pH
Batch 1	6.720
Batch 2	6.810
Batch 3	6.750
Average	6.766

Showing the Percentage of Heavy Metals (in ppm) for *Swalpa Khadir Vatika* - Table no.17.

Heavy metals (in ppm)	Limit (in ppm)	<i>Swalpa Khadir Vatika</i>		
		Batch I	Batch II	Batch III
Mercury	Up to 1	0.16	0.16	0.16
Arsenic	Up to 3	0.45	0.45	0.45
Cadmium	Up to 0.3	0.09	0.09	0.09
Lead	Up to 10	0.47	0.47	0.47

Showing the Total Microbial Load (Cfu/gm) for *Swalpa Khadir Vatika*-Table no.18.

Samples	Total Plate Load (Microbial) (Cfu/gm) for <i>Swalpa Khadir Vatika</i>
Batch 1	20
Batch 2	22
Batch 3	21
Average	21

Results of HPTLC study of (All the samples of *Swalpa Khadir Vatika*)

- ❖ Presence of CATECHIN content in mobile phase - (Toulene: Ethylacetate: Formic acid 5:4:0.2)
- ❖ Methanolic extract of all samples with Quercetin marker were run in solvent system of Toulene:Ethylacetate:Formic acid (5:4:0.2).

- ❖ The plate was observed under UV wavelength of 254 nm and 366 nm and the presence of the marker compound CATECHIN was detected in all the sample.
- ❖ The presence of marker compound catechin in the sample *Swalpa Khadir Vatika* is 64.3004 ng/ml.

The HPTLC analysis of SKV20 confirmed the presence of Catechin, validated through comparison with the reference standard. The obtained R_f value and peak pattern matched closely with the standard Catechin profile. The quantitative estimation revealed Catechin content of 51.63 ng/mL, indicating that the formulation maintains its phytochemical integrity. Thus, HPTLC proves to be an effective tool for standardizing SKV20, ensuring quality, authenticity, and therapeutic consistency of the formulation.

CONCLUSION

Pharmaceutical and analytical standardisation of *Swalpa Khadir Vatika* establishes a scientific framework for ensuring the quality, safety, and reproducibility of this classical Ayurvedic formulation. The systematic evaluation of raw materials, adherence to classical pharmaceutical procedures, and assessment through organoleptic, physicochemical, and analytical parameters confirm the authenticity and consistency of the prepared formulation. The findings highlight that proper standardisation not only preserves the therapeutic integrity described in classical texts but also enhances acceptability in contemporary clinical practice and research. This study provides baseline reference standards that can be utilised for quality control, large-scale production, and further pharmacological and clinical investigations, thereby contributing to the evidence-based integration of Ayurvedic formulations into modern healthcare systems.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I am very thankful to my Guide and co-guide Dr. Rajeev Narayan Bilas and Dr. Anjana Dwivedi respectively for continuous support during research work & Mr. Arvind Kumar Katiyar, Gov. Analyst, State Pharmacy of Ayurved & Unani Drugs, Tikaitrai Talab, Lucknow and Cytogene research and laboratory, industrial area, Lucknow for the analytical study of raw drugs and final product i.e; *Swalpa Khadir Vatika*.

Conflicts of Interest

No academic or financial Conflict of Interest.

REFERENCES

1. Sen GD. Bhaishajya Ratnavali. Mukharoga Chikitsa Adhyaya. Chapter 61, verses 101–103. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan; Reprint ed. (2005).

2. Tripathi B., Sharangdhara, Madhyama Khanda - Chapter 1/1, Sharangadhara Samhita, Varanasi: Chaukhamba Surbharti Prakashan; 2012; 125.
3. Tripathi B., Sharangdhara, Madhyama Khanda - Chapter 2, Sharangadhara Samhita, Varanasi: Chaukhamba Surbharti Prakashan; 2012; 89.
4. Pharmacopeia commission for Indian Medicine and Homeopathy, Ministry of Ayush, Gov. of India.
5. Sarangadhara, Sarangadhara Samhita, Md. Kh. 2/1 - 2, Commentary by Dr.Brahmanand Tripathi, Chaukhamba Surbharti Prakashana, Varanasi, 2010; 92.
6. Chakradatt by Vaidya Ravi Datt Shastri 2012 edition-(1/115).
7. Sharngdhara Samhita commentary by Dr Brahmanand Tripathi, Chaukhamba publications-2022 madyam khanda 2 / 1-2, p-90.
8. Kulkarni D.A., Rasaratansamuccaya, vijnana Boddhini commentary, Ed-2006, New Delhi, Meharchand Laxmandas Publication; verse 10/2.
9. Government of India, Ministry of AYUSH. The Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India, Part I, Volume I. New Delhi: Controller of Publications; Monograph: Khadira (*Acacia catechu*).
10. Government of India, Ministry of AYUSH. The Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India, Part I, Volume I. New Delhi: Controller of Publications; Monograph: Puga (*Areca catechu*).
11. Government of India, Ministry of AYUSH. The Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India, Part I, Volume I. New Delhi: Controller of Publications; Monograph: Jatiphala/Javitri (*Myristica fragrans*).
12. Government of India, Ministry of AYUSH. The Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India, Part I, Volume I. New Delhi: Controller of Publications; Monograph: Kankola (*Piper cubeba*).
13. Government of India, Ministry of AYUSH. The Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India, Part I, Volume II. New Delhi: Controller of Publications; Monograph: Karpoora (*Cinnamomum camphora*).